

Composition and Characterisation of some Metal Complexes of 2,5-Dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone

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2,5-Dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone shows chelating properties owing to the presence of hydroxyl and keto groups. The hydroxyl groups at positions 2 and 5 being highly acidic lead to the formation of anion with relative ease.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses data support the formulations proposed for the complexes (Table 1).

The infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes support the above formulations proposed for these complexes. Comparison of the spectra of the complexes with that of the ligand shows shifts in principal bands due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-O} modes which occur at 1 610 and 1 210 cm^{-1} in the ligand. For all the complexes the $\nu_{C=O}$ frequency shifted to lower values (1 590–1 440 cm^{-1}), thereby confirming the

coordination of the metal ions through the oxygens of the hydroxyl and the carbonyl group. The ν_{C-O} frequency also shifted (1 320–1 250 cm^{-1}) suggesting the above mode of coordination. In addition, new bands appear as a result of ν_{M-O} or $\nu_{M-O+C-C}$ stretching modes. These vibrational modes appear at 550 in Fe^{III} , 720 in Co^{II} , 550 in Ni^{II} , 740 in Cu^{II} , 500 in Zr^{IV} , 720 in Ba^{II} , 700 in Sr^{II} , 760 in Mg^{II} , 690 in Hg^{II} and 750 cm^{-1} in Ag^{I} complexes. The infrared spectra thus unambiguously confirm the formation of the complexes and the donor sites in the ligand¹.

The electronic absorption spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurement of the complexes further elucidate the nature and the configuration of the complexes (Table 1). The Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes are spin-free octahedral. The Cu^{II} complex is tetragonally distorted with four short metal ligand bonds along Z-axis above and below this plane². The Zr^{IV} complex has triangular dodecahedral geometry³. The Ba^{II} and Sr^{II} complexes have octahedral stereochemistry⁴. The Co^{II} complex has an octahedral environment with little orbital contribution caused by distortion in the complex.

The thermal analysis data for two representative complexes are as follows : TGA loss in mass %

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex (Colour)	Analysis%: Found/(Calcd.)			λ_{\max} (cm ⁻¹) (assignments)	μ_{eff} B.M.
	C	H	N		
[Fe(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄) _{1.5}] _n (Black)	52.51 (52.17)	1.49 (1.44)	27.10 (26.97)	40 912 (CT) 28 571 (⁴ T ₁ ← ⁶ A _{1g}) 25 000 (⁴ A _{1g} ← ⁴ E _g (C _s) ←) 14 285 (⁴ T _{2g} ←)	5.70
[Co(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O] _n (Chocolate)	31.82 (30.91)	3.21 (2.57)	25.12 (25.29)	40 000 (CT) 20 408 (⁴ T _{1g} (P) ← ⁴ T _{1g}) 16 949 (⁴ T _{2g} ← ⁴ T _{1g}) 10 333 (⁴ T _{1g} ← ⁴ T _{1g})	4.00
[Ni(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O] _n (Violet)	30.30 (30.28)	3.00 (2.52)	26.00 (26.93)	38 461 (CT) 28 169 (⁸ T _{1g} (P) ← ³ A _{2g}) 25 974 (¹ T _{1g} ← ³ A _{2g}) 16 920 (¹ T _{1g} ← ³ A ₂) 10 512 (³ T _{1g} ← ³ A _{2g})	3.20
[Cu(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O] _n (Brownish green)	30.26 (30.31)	2.95 (2.52)	27.51 (26.74)	40 120, 29 411 (CT)	1.80
[Zr(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄) _n (Brown)	39.01 (39.21)	2.03 (1.08)	24.99 (24.84)	40 000, 28 571, 15 873 (CT)	—
[Ba(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O] _n (Pale brown)	24.15 (23.12)	2.10 (1.92)	45.00 (44.11)	38 461, 34 482, 31 250, 27 771, 20 408 (CT)	—
[Sr(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O] _n (Light brown)	30.95 (31.91)	2.52 (2.29)	23.25 (23.49)	35 120, 17 212 (CT)	—
[Mg(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄).2HO] _n (Dark purple)	31.98 (32.38)	2.78 (2.69)	11.00 (10.93)	27 100, 19 047 (CT)	—
[Co(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O] _n	—	—	—	40 000 (CT) 20 408 (⁴ T _{1g} (P) ← ⁴ T _{1g}) 16 949 (⁴ A _{2g} ← ⁴ T _{1g}) 10 333 (⁴ T _{2g} ← ⁴ T _{1g})	4.00
[Hg(C ₆ H ₂ O ₄) _n (Chocolate)	16.02 (16.41)	0.83 (0.45)	32.31 (31.46)	28 925, 18 181 (M ← L CT ^a)	—
[Ag ₂ (C ₆ H ₂ O ₄)] (Black)	20.99 (20.36)	0.60 (0.56)	59.21 (60.97)	23 529, 14 285 (M ← L CT ^a)	—

^aRef. 2.

Found (calcd.) for [Cu(C₆H₂O₄).2H₂O]_n, 1st step 5.29 (5.00), 2nd step 25.50 (25.00); [Ag₂(C₆H₂O₄)], final step 20.12 (20.25). The results support the proposed chemical compositions and structures.

The DTA curve of the Ag^I complex shows no endothermic peak, i.e. corresponding to the loss of water molecules, but it shows one exothermic peak at 427°, which indicates the absence of water molecules in this complex. The DTA curve of the Cu^{II} complex shows one endothermic peak at 243° and one strong exothermic peak at 427°. The first arrest in TGA curves corresponding to DTA peaks of the Cu^{II} complex show a weight loss of 5.29% (calcd. 5.00%) due to the elimination of water molecules. In the light of spectral, magnetic and thermal studies, it can be inferred that water molecules are coordinated to the metal ion. The rapid decomposition of the Cu^{II} complex starts after the loss of coordinated water molecules. No intermediates could be isolated and characterised because of their

unstable nature. The final products are the corresponding metal oxides.

It is concluded that 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone has two chelating sites provided by two carbonyl functions and their two adjacent hydroxyls. This peculiar structural characteristic of the ligand make the complexes to be polymeric in nature. The coordinated water molecules make up the required coordination number.

Experimental

2,5-Dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone was prepared by the reported procedure⁵.

The metal complexes in all cases were prepared by mixing the metal ion and the ligand in stoichiometric ratio (determined from solution studies) in water. The complexes precipitated from concentrated solutions were dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

NOTES

The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and the electronic spectra on a Carl-Ziess VSU2P spectrophotometer. Estimations of C and H were carried out by microanalytical technique. The metal content was estimated by ignition of the complexes to their respective oxides following usual analytical procedures. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by Gouy method. The simultaneous DTG and DTA curves were obtained on a Paulik-Paulik-Erdey MOM derivatograph (Hungary) at a heating rate of $10^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

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